

EMBRYONIC DEVELOPMENT, ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE OF THE SPHENOID BONE, AND ITS ROLE IN THE PNEUMATIZATION OF THE SPHENOID SINUS

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Abstract

The sphenoid bone forms through a complex process of endochondral and membranous ossification, beginning as early as the 8th week of gestation. This process involves numerous paired ossification centers that form both the main body of the bone and its processes—the greater and lesser wings and the pterygoid processes. During the prenatal and early postnatal periods, a gradual fusion of these structures occurs, completing in the first year after birth. Anatomically, the sphenoid bone plays a central role in forming the base of the skull, connecting with 12 other bones and shaping important anatomical structures such as the sella turcica, the optic canal, and the sphenoid processes. It also includes the sphenoid sinuses, whose pneumatization begins as early as the fifth month of pregnancy. The clinical significance of these structures is linked to their proximity to neurovascular structures and the possibility of surgical access through them. A detailed understanding of the embryonic development and anatomy of the sphenoid bone is of key importance for neurosurgical and otoneurological interventions in this region.

Keywords: sphenoid bone, embryonic development, ossification, endochondral ossification, membranous ossification, pterygoid process, greater and lesser wings, sella turcica, sphenoid sinus, skull base, anatomical relationships.

Introduction

The sphenoid bone (*os sphenoidale*) is a central structure at the base of the skull and plays an important role in the anatomical and functional organization of the skull base. It participates in the formation of the anterior and middle cranial fossae and is in close spatial relation to important neurovascular structures such as the optic nerve, the internal carotid artery, and the pituitary gland [1,2]. The embryonic development of the sphenoid bone is particularly complex and occurs through a combination of endochondral and membranous ossification, with the process beginning as early as the eighth gestational week [3,4]. The development and degree of pneumatization of the sphenoid sinuses vary significantly among individuals and have a significant impact on the choice of surgical approach for interventions in the pituitary region and the ventral skull base [5,6]. A thorough understanding of the embryological and anatomical characteristics of this bone is essential for the planning and safe performance of transsphenoidal surgeries, particularly in light of individual variations [7,8].

Discussion

The sphenoid bone develops from seven paired ossification centers, primarily through the endochondral method of bone growth. Only minimal foci of membranous ossification can be detected. The site of ossification of the greater wing and the lateral pterygoid plate arises between the foramen ovale and the foramen rotundum during the 8th gestational week of pregnancy (*alisphenoidale*). During the 9th week, a point located on the lateral part of the optic canal can be detected,

which is designated for the lesser wing (*orbito-sphenoidale*) [1–6]. The body ossifies based on two pairs of points located one after the other: the posterior pair forms the so-called *basissphenoidale* and develops during the third month of pregnancy in the floor of the sella turcica, while the anterior pair (which develops later than the posterior pair) forms the *presphenoidale* portion. Lateral to the *basissphenoidale*, a small punctate ossification develops for the tongue of the sphenoid and the adjacent part of the carotid sulcus, which soon fuses with the *basissphenoidale*. The ossification points of the *basissphenoidale* fuse with one another during the 4th month of fetal development. The ossification points of the lesser wing and the sphenoid body fuse bilaterally at the same time, while the two separate sphenoid bodies fuse, as well as with the *basissphenoidale*, only in the 8th month (the cartilage located between the anterior and posterior pairs of ossification points of the body regresses before or shortly after birth). A separate ossification center on the medial part of the pterygoid bone appears during the 2nd month of embryonic development, via membranous ossification [3,4,6,9]. The latter is also a process of development of a small center at the tip of the greater wing. All other ossification centers develop through endochondral ossification. The neonatal sphenoid bone consists of three parts: right and left, comprising the greater wing and the pterygoid process; and a central part that develops from already fused ossification centers. These three parts, connected by a thin layer of cartilage, fuse during the first postnatal year. The sphenoid sinuses develop

from the primitive skull at several ossification sites, beginning in the fifth month of pregnancy [2,8].

Anatomical structure of the sphenoid bone.

The sphenoid bone (os sphenoidale) is located in the center of the cranial base and connects with 12 bones, forming the anterior and middle cranial fossae:

❖ Single: Vomer; Ethmoid bone; Frontal bone; Occipital bone.

❖ Pairs: Parietal bones; Temporal bones; Zygomatic bone; Palatine bones.

The sphenoid bone consists of a body and three symmetrical processes: the greater and lesser wings, and the pterygoid process. The body (corpus) is the central part of the bone, and its shape is similar to a cube. This is why we distinguish six main surfaces: anterior, posterior, superior, inferior, and two lateral. The posterior side of the body connects to the clivus of the occipital bone via the sphenoid-occipital synchondrosis. The anterior part of the body forms the sphenoid crest, which connects anteriorly to the perpendicular plate of the ethmoid bone and continues inferiorly as the sphenoid rostrum. On either side of the sphenoid crest lie the sphenoid conchae. Lateral to and superior to the conchae are the openings of the sphenoid sinuses, which lead to the sphenoid sinus and are located in the body of the sphenoid bone [9,10–13]. On the inferior surface of the body, the sphenoid rostrum is visible, which is surrounded by the wings of the vomer. The carotid sulci are located bilaterally on either side of the body. Posterior and lateral to these sulci lies the sphenoid lingula, which is situated in the lower part of the head. The greater wings and the medial pterygoid plates articulate with the lateral surfaces of the sphenoid body. The upper surface, facing the cranial fossa, exhibits a coronally situated depression—the fossa hypophysialis (pituitary fossa). The sella is bordered posteriorly by the dorsum sellae, which terminates laterally with posterior sphenoid processes. The sphenoid processes may be united in the form of bony bridges that connect these processes unilaterally or bilaterally. The posterior part of the dorsum sellae slopes downward and, together with the basilar part of the occiput, forms the clivus (of Blumenbach). The anterior part of the upper surface of the body is occupied by the medial cuneiform processes. In the anterior part of the sella tuber, there is a transversely oriented prechiasmatic sulcus, which continues bilaterally as the optic canals. The anterior border of this sulcus is the sphenoidal limb, followed by the sphenoidal plane, with the anterior margin of this plane forming the ethmoidal spine [9-12].

The greater wings of the sphenoid bone (ala major os sphenoidale) are the largest sphenoid processes and

are attached to the lateral part of the body via a root (radix). The posterior part of the wing forms the process known as the sphenoid spine. There are two distinct surfaces of the greater wing: the inner (intracranial) and the outer (extracranial) surfaces. The cerebral surface forms part of the floor of the lateral aspect of the middle cranial fossa. The external surface can be divided into: orbital, temporal, infratemporal, and maxillary surfaces. The last three surfaces are the posterior walls of the temporal, infratemporal, and pterygopalatine fossae. The greater wing contains the foramen rotundum, ovale, and spinosum, as well as the variable foramen Vesalii. The upper margin of the orbital surface of the greater wing of the sphenoid bone borders the superior orbital fissure inferiorly, and its lower margin borders the inferior orbital fissure [12,13,14].

The lesser wings of the sphenoid bone (ala minor os sphenoidale) originate medially in the superoanterior part of the sphenoid body from two roots that form the optic canal. In the middle, the two lesser wings join the jugum of the sphenoid body. The superior surface of the lesser wings forms part of the floor of the anterior cranial fossa. The posterior border is situated at the anterior cuneiform process [13,15].

The pterygoid processes (processus pterygoideus) originate bilaterally from the junction between the body and the greater wing and project downward. They consist of the medial and lateral pterygoid plates. These plates join anteriorly to form the pterygo-palatine sulcus. Posteriorly, the two plates enclose the pterygoid fossa. In the lower part, the lamellae are separated by the pterygoid notch. The base of the pterygoid process is pierced by the pterygoid canal (Vidian). The scaphoid fossa is located immediately adjacent to the base. The anterior wall of the process forms the posterior wall of the pterygopalatine fossa, and the lateral surface of the outer pterygoid plate forms a portion of the medial wall of the infratemporal fossa. At the lower end of the medial pterygoid plate is the pterygoid hamulus, and on its lateral surface is the groove of the hamulus. A process extends from the root of the medial pterygoid plate [4–8, 12–15]. The vomerovaginal groove is located on the inferior surface of this process. A distinct groove is present between the body of the sphenoid and the process. The body of the sphenoid bone is almost entirely composed of compact bone. Small remnants of ossification are found in the posterior part of the body, at the bases of the pterygoid processes, in the thicker parts of the greater wings, and on the posterior surfaces of the lesser wings (Figures 1 and 2) [15,16,17].

Figure 1. Sphenoid bone – view from above.

Figure 2. Rear view of the sphenoid bone.

The pneumatization of the sphenoid bone is a key process in the embryonic and postnatal development of the sphenoid sinus and has direct clinical significance in transsphenoidal surgical procedures. The onset of this process can be traced as early as the fifth month of intrauterine development, when epithelial invaginations from the nasal cavity begin to penetrate the body of the sphenoid bone [1,2,10-17]. The formation of the sphenoid sinus occurs through the invasion of respiratory epithelium, which resorbs bone tissue, allowing for the expansion and formation of an air-filled cavity. As the sinus grows, significant morphological variations occur, resulting in different degrees of pneumatization—ranging from conchal and presellar to sellar and postsellar types [3,15,17].

There are individual differences in the volume and shape of pneumatization, which depend on genetic and environmental factors, and in pathological conditions (e.g., chronic sinusitis), delayed or aberrant development of the sinus may be observed [4,9,17]. The sellar and postsellar types of pneumatization, in which the sinus extends below and behind the sella turcica, are of great importance for surgical anatomy, as they provide better access to the pituitary gland, but also increase the risk of intraoperative injury to neurovascular structures such as the internal carotid artery and the optic canals [5,6,10,14].

Pneumatization of the sphenoid bone is not limited to its body—in some cases, it also involves the bases of

the greater wings, the pterygoid processes, and occasionally the clivus. Such extensive pneumatization creates anatomical challenges during interventions in the craniocervical region and may compromise the stability of the bony structure [7]. This is precisely why preoperative evaluation via high-resolution CT or MRI is mandatory, especially in patients with suspected anatomical variation or tumor invasion [8,13-17].

Last but not least, the degree of pneumatization also correlates with age—maximum expansion is usually achieved after puberty, and in some individuals, the process continues into the third decade of life. Clinicians and surgeons should bear in mind that a hyperpneumatized sphenoid sinus may even involve protrusion of the carotid canal or the optic nerve, which significantly increases the risk of intraoperative complications [9,15-17].

Conclusion

The sphenoid bone represents a key anatomical and embryonic element at the base of the human skull. Through a complex and coordinated process of ossification, it forms important structures that participate both in shaping the skull base and in providing access to intracranial regions. Understanding its morphogenesis is essential for the precise performance of transsphenoidal and craniocervical surgical interventions.

References

1. Watanabe K, Rhoton AL Jr, Origitano TC, Ono M. Sphenoid sinus: microsurgical anatomy and surgical

- approaches. *Neurosurgery*. 1990;26(1):44–58. doi: 10.1227/00006123-199001000-00008.
2. Renn WH, Rhoton AL Jr. Microsurgical anatomy of the sellar region. *J Neurosurg*. 1975;43(3):288–298. doi: 10.3171/jns.1975.43.3.0288.
 3. Lang J. *Clinical Anatomy of the Head: Neurocranium, Orbit, Craniocervical Regions*. Springer; 1983.
 4. Duvernoy HM. *The Human Brain: Surface, Three-Dimensional Sectional Anatomy with MRI, and Blood Supply*. Springer; 1999.
 5. Güldner C, Diogo I, De Vos N, et al. Imaging anatomy of the sphenoid sinus. *Head Neck*. 2012;34(2):203–210. doi:10.1002/hed.21716.
 6. Unal B, Bademci G, Bilgili YK, Batay F, Avci E. Risky anatomic variations of sphenoid sinus for surgery. *Surg Radiol Anat*. 2006;28(2):195–201. doi: 10.1007/s00276-005-0071-5.
 7. Cappabianca P, Cavallo LM, Esposito F, et al. Endoscopic endonasal transsphenoidal surgery: anatomy, technique, and complications. *Neurosurg Focus*. 2005;19(6):E2. doi: 10.3171/foc.2005.19.6.3.
 8. Fernández-Miranda JC, Gardner PA, Prevedello DM, Kassam AB. Expanded endonasal approach for cranial base and brain stem tumors: anatomical study and clinical considerations. *Neurosurg Focus*. 2009;25(6):E22. doi: 10.3171/2009.9.FOCUS09187.
 9. Tatreau JR, Patel MR, Shah RN, et al. Anatomical considerations for endoscopic endonasal skull base surgery. *Neurosurg Focus*. 2011;30(5):E8. doi: 10.3171/2011.2.FOCUS117
 10. Maru YK, Gupta V. Anatomical variations of sphenoid sinus and their clinical importance. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2014;66(1):39–45. doi:10.1007/s12070-011-0477-y
 11. Hewaidi G, Omami G. Anatomic variation of sphenoid sinus and related structures in Libyan population: CT scan study. *Libyan J Med*. 2008;3(3):128–133. doi: 10.3402/ljm.v3i3.4755
 12. Delano MC, Fun FY, Zinreich SJ. Relationship of the optic nerve to the posterior paranasal sinuses: a CT anatomical study. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol*. 1996;17(4):669–675. PMID: 8733972
 13. Wang J, Bidari S, Inoue K, Yang H, Rhoton AL Jr. Extensions of the sphenoid sinus: a new classification. *Neurosurgery*. 2010;66(4):797–816. doi: 10.1227/01.NEU.0000367619.24852.B1
 14. Hamid O, El Fiky L, Hassan O, Kotb A, El Fiky S. Anatomic variations of the sphenoid sinus and their impact on trans-sphenoid pituitary surgery. *Skull Base*. 2008;18(1):9–15. doi: 10.1055/s-2007-992764
 15. Kazkayasi M, Karadeniz Y, Arıkan OK. Anatomic variations of the sphenoid sinus. *Neurosurg Rev*. 2005;28(1):42–46. doi: 10.1007/s10143-004-0368-2
 16. Sirikci A, Bayazit YA, Bayram M, Mumbruç S, Güngör K, Kanlikama M. Variations of sphenoid and related structures. *Eur Radiol*. 2000;10(5):844–848. doi: 10.1007/s003300051052
 17. Kantarci M, Karasen RM, Alper F, et al. Remarkable anatomic variations of the sphenoid sinus. *Eur J Radiol*. 2004;50(3):299–303. doi: 10.1016/j.ejrad.2003.07.003